

Original Article

The Role of Dr. Khan Sahib in Promoting Education in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa during (1937-47)

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Abstract

These stories highlight Dr. Khan Sahib's (1882-1958) educational struggle alongside his efforts to uplift the educational opportunities across the province. He was the chief minister multiple times – thrice before independence – in the Indian British North-West Frontier Province. His tenure as the Prime Minister from 1937, then in 1945 and 1946 is somewhat an ignored paradigm of the history, specifically for the focus on education. This paper aims to scrutinize the work of Dr. Khan Sahib in the development of education in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, the former North West Frontier Province during British rule. Dr. Khan single handedly set up more than fifty primary schools and seventeen secondary schools and was in the process of executing a grand design with plans to establish the University of Peshawar which was later completed by Haji Qayyum in 1952.

Keywords: Dr. Khan Sahib, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Education

Introduction

Dr. Khan Sahib's biography states that he was born in the home of Mohammadzay tribe, in the village of Utmanzai, Charsadda in 1882. His father, Bahram Khan, was the chief of the clan, but showed little pride in this title. As far as Khan Sahib is concerned, family customs and documents of identity card and passport suggest that his original name was Khan Sahib. It appears custom demanded 'sahib' be affixed to relatives' names, two of who were Shah Sahib and Mir Sahib. We can only guess that his birth name was Abdul Jabbar Khan, as no other information is available in historical literature (Kamal, n.d.).

Saddaullah Khan, his son, even at one moment said in one of the meetings in his village that he has no idea who Abdul Jabbar Khan is, but yes, Dr Khan Sahib was his father. This doctor took his initial learning from the Municipal Board high school which is located in Peshawar. He also completed his Matric from Edwards Memorial Mission School, Peshawar. At that time, in 1905, Edwards Mission school was linked to University of Punjab. Subsequently, he enrolled in a medical college in Bombay. His further studies were pursued in England where he took up Medicine as well as practicing in London. He worked as a Medical Officer in the Indian Army, holding the rank of Captain, and was stationed in France from 1911 to 1914. For thirteen years, he was out of the country which included doing MRCS in St Thomas Hospital in London. When he did come back in 1920, he had no clue about what his province was going through and neither did he know about his father and younger brother, Abdul Ghaffar also known as Bacha Khan (Khaliq, 1972).

He served with the Mardan Guides but was later sent to Waziristan for action against the local populace which he chose not to do. I remember struggling quite a bit, but finally in 1921, I was able to get my resignation. Subsequently, he practiced as a doctor and operated a medical clinic in the Qissa Khawani bazar and became known for it. In addition, he also ran a clinic from his home village of Utmanzai and used to attend to patients during the weekend. Dr. Khan Sahib was married twice. First, he wed a woman called Khurshida Bibi of Duaba, Charsadda. From this wife he had Sadullah Khan, Ubaidullah Khan, and Hidayatullah Khan, his three sons.

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Sadullah Khan had two grandsons, Shamim Sadullah and Anwar Sadullah. Ubaidullah Khan had three grandsons: Munir, Jan, and another. Hondyadullah Khan had three grandsons, Mustafa Kamal, Ajmal Kham, and Sheriyar Khan. While in London, Dr. Khan Sahib married a Scottish woman, Marry. They were blessed with a son, Jan Khan, and a daughter, Maryam (Khan, 2022).

Dr. Khan Sahib Entrance into Freedom Movement

In 1921, along with some notables and scholars, Bacha Khan, the younger brother of Dr. Khan Sahib, founded Anjumani Islahul Afaghina with the motivation of changing the Pashtun society towards social betterment. This was the first systematic organization owned by all Pashtuns. AIA established as many as 134 Azad Islamia Schools in the province. It was an alternate educational system set up in opposition to the British which sought to turn citizens into government lackies (Ghaffar, 1946).

The Anjuma's educational system was an alternate model, aimed at producing the sons of the soil. The Anjuman worked tirelessly until 1929; however, to give more political space, another organisation was established named the 'Khudai Khidmatgar movement' in September 1929. The British Raj felt the twin organisations were a threat to their legacy. Therefore, they started arresting Bacha Khan and his colleagues. The Khudai Khidmagaar movement was an organised organisation that used to arrange camps in villages, trained their workers, educated the illiterate members, and did parades. Dr. Khan Sahib, initially reluctant to the KK movement, was impressed later and started lecturing in the camps about the discipline, literacy, social activism, freedom, and real purpose of life.

In Nowshere he delivered a speech in Khudai Khidmatgar camp, in which he mentioned the theme of his talk as, "My dear brothers, Today, I want to talk on the subject of discipline; the progress, freedom, and welfare of the country depend on it" (Sultan-i-Rome, 2013).

On July 23, 1940, the Khilafat movement created a hub for mobilization in Sardaryab. Dr. Khan used to come to Markaz Alia in Sardaryab and used to give many lectures on first aid, self-medication, and self-discipline. He remarked once: "Kuhdai Khidmatgar system is a military-like arrangement, so there must be discipline which is its sine qua non. As you know, the management of our homes and Hujras is always in a mess. The foremost reason for this is absence of discipline. The truth of the matter is, there are many to command but no one to follow." Dr. Khan noted, "I have made it clear that aggression and non-aggression are two military terms of stict disciplines. ...our is a voluntary organisatory; there is no salary in it. An individual can work efficiently in our organization on the condition that his participation is voluntary and he performs his duties with eagerness. Most of the people are content until they are paid as officers or generals, but when they are dismissed, then they no longer feel at home" (Azad, 1989).

He further explained that “it is an uphill task, as I know, to maintain discipline. When you lodge a complaint against your subordinate, it must be in such a manner that he gets his due, but he should not be humiliated. I know my story of the war times. I was on my duty in the camp. One day a general came; he asked me to accompany. He discussed with me different incidents; later, when it came into the knowledge of the camp commander, he became furious with me. Once I was ignorant about a new order that was promulgated during my leave and could not obey it (Nehru, 1946).

I explained my position; still, I was reported. That is why I emphasise that if you want to report any Khudai Khidmatgar member, do not distort the facts about him because it creates rifts. The English in the army take care of it, but the Indians do not pay any heed to it. The result is factions are established. The Khattak soldiers accompany the Khattaks and the Yousafzais, building their own clique. These splinter groups are the odds and ends of our slavery; if we are Pakhtuns, we should live together. My brothers, I believe that lectures and sermons cannot make us good. The real way is that we should reform ourselves first. Another major flaw in our camp is that though we have allotted ample time for prayers, meals, and parades, when the lecture starts, many come late with excuses that they were saying their prayers. These things are diametrically opposed to the concept of discipline. If an officer is ordered to go get himself a drone in the sea, he has no right to ask why.”

Dr. Khan Sahib entered into the main activities of the Khudai Khidmatgar Movement and got connected with the political and social sphere of the movements. It should be noted here that he was not keen to make a contribution. After the Qissa Khwani Massacre on 30th April, 1930, when the Farangi Raaj killed 272 Rakshas (272 innocent citizens), and on the same day Bacha Khan with his fellow Khudai Khidmatgars were arrested, Dr. Khan Sahib took a plunge in politics and assumed the second tier leadership of the movement. The story as told by Dr. Khan Sahib himself goes like this: A meeting was due the following day in Utmanzai, and some level of violence was likely. For that reason I drove down from Peshawar to Utmanzai. I got to the area some hours before the set time, and managed to capture all the weapons that people had. Here in Utmanzai, I gave my first political speech in a public gathering. When I wrapped up my address, some people told me that the Cavalry guides were on their way. I told them who wished to be surrender to this situation ought to leave the meeting. But surprisingly no one left the venue. I asked for the red shirts so that they could rise to the platform. The commander of the cavalry informed that there was going to be firing and the gathering needed to be broken up.

Though the people were indifferent. The commander posed the question regarding my assistance in a rather direct way. And I reasoned that the most prudent course of action would be to retreat as the meeting is adjourned and we shall instead march towards our bearing. It is now or never; if you intend to fire, get it over with. If we set off for a march to the firing range, it would not be a courageous action. The commander intended to outsmart me, but he ultimately withdraw with his troops. The Red Shirts have been escorted with their bands and have been commanded to march to an area close to a mosque. The bands have been split into two and are being commanded to march to their respective locations. The Red Shirt Salar Aslam Khan was their commander, instructed them to get down on their belly. The soldiers began to charge at them but halted mere inches from the front line. This time the ground forces will suddenly lose all forms of discipline and self-control. The March of the Red Shirts reached a total of eighty thousand by September nineteen thirty.

Role of Dr Khan sahib Ministry in Promotion of Education

The Title of ‘Governor’s Province’ was received by the region on January 25, 1932, given through several painful efforts involving community mobilization paired with bargaining at the second tier of the roundtable conference by both local and national institutions. With so many reforms happening, the British government incorporated the system of communal electorates within the province in 1935. Both communal electorates and the over-centralized special powers of the Governor General were the main reasons for disaffection for the Congress and in particular for the Khudai Khidmatgars in the context of the reform package. The Governor-General possessed the right to declare a state of emergency, dissolve the republic, and assume all powers.

The British government established a mechanism to drive a wedge between two groups in order to extend their power. Every time a solution was on the verge of being achieved, the administration. "The government would take some action that upset the balance whenever a settlement was almost reached" (Marwat, 2012).

Following their designation as an illegal association under the 1935 Act, the Khudai Khidmatgar movement was registered with the Congress parliamentary board. Nevertheless, the administration attempted to suppress the Congressional Parliamentary Board's election campaigning efforts by every means possible (Khan, 1995).

Thus, Kamdar Khan of Kalu Khan and Abdullah Shah of Mazara were also complicit in the illegal activities of an organization. It sufficed for any of the election Russian campaigns—Islam Zindabad or Fakhre Afghan Zindabad—to warrant a judgement against the KKs. With all these hurdles, a 50-member provincial assembly was elected in February 1937. The Government concentrated all its power to win over parliament within the open battle.

The moment a settlement was about to be achieved, the Khudai Khidmatgar movement received recognition from the Congress parliamentary board after feedback was registered as an unlawful association under the 1935 Act. 'The government would take some action that upset the balance' is a common saying. Somehow, the government sought to contain the epidemic of congressional parliamentary board campaigning. For assisting the operation of an unlawful association, both Abdullah Shah of Mazara as well as Kamdar Khan of Kalu Khan were tried and convicted. Islam Zindabad or Fakhre Afghan Zindabad—any of these campaign slogans would get the KKs convicted. These candidates were supported by the Congressional party, and despite everything, a provincial assembly of 50 members was elected in February! The administration sought to consolidate all of its strength against the congressional candidates.

Even so, a good portion of the regime's supporters were defeated. Out of the 35 seats that were up for grabs, Khudai Khidmatgars received 19, Hindu-Sikh party received 8, Azad Party got 3, while independent candidates held 16. Sahibzada Abdul Qayum Khan was appointed the chief minister of the province with George Cunningham's backing. Rai Bahadur Mehr Chan Khanna took over the finance portfolio while Asad Ullah Khan Bahadur became the minister of agriculture. Speaker was Khuda Bakhsh Malik and his deputy became Sarwar Muhammad (Ghaffar, 1938, May 1).

However, the regime that was put in place didn't endure for long. A no-confidence motion was passed during the Legislative Assembly meeting on September 3, 1937, with a vote of 27 'no' and 22 'yes.' The administration was set up by Dr. Khan. Sahib on the 7th of September in 1937. Muhammad Abbas Khan held the position of the Health Minister, while Lala Bhanju Ram Ghandi took over Finance and Qazi Attaullah Khan took over Education. The four parliamentary secretaries were Amir Muhmmaad Khan, Arbab Abdul Ghafoor Khan, Rai Bahadur Chaman Lal and Barrister Abdul Ghafoor Khan.

Dr. Khan's Shahib Government was in power until September 3, 1939. It not only helped in social development but also in the educational advancement of the society. Marked in every way was the setting up of additional fifty primary schools for boys and ten for girls during the two years. The budgetary allocation was also raised to Rs. 29 lacs and, for the first time, a significant portion was frozen for the education of women.

In October of the year 1938, Qazi Attaullah, the honorable educational minister, presented the N.W.F.P. primary education compulsory bill for the assembly. The discussion was participated by Rai Bahadur Mehr Chand Khanna, Arbab Abdul Ghafoor Khan, Pir Bakhsh, Abdul Rab Nishatr, Mian Jaffer Shah, Sardar Aurangzeb Khan, Ajit Singh and Amir Mohammed Khan. Mian Jaffer Shah, a member of the legislature from Khudai Khidmatgar had started a bill to facilitate Pashto as the principal language of instruction.

In advancing his argument, he cited Bengal, Sindh, and Gujarat as cases where children were educated in their mother tongue. Some of the minorities claimed that the Anjuman-i-Himayat Islam literature which was mandatory in the case of the Sikhs and the Hindus, should be removed. This was accepted by Dr. Khan Sahib's cabinet which allowed the Muslim League to wage an aggressive counteroffensive campaign against him (Shah, 1999).

Anjuman-i-Himayat Islam succeeded in setting up a high school in Peshawar City and enforced their own curriculum in the DB schools in 1936. On the contrary, the minority community which had established seven out of eight schools in the city didn't factor into this decision at all. The Education Minister, Qazi Attaullah, bluntly remarked that the books should be supplanted with other Anjuman titles, and that there are no restrictions in cases when there are no Sikh or Hindu students present.

In September 1939, on the eve of the Central Congress Committee, the ministry resigned its position because it had already broken the trust of the Indian populace during the Second World War. The ministry awarded 940 scholarships which pleased several constituents, including 93 non-Muslim recipients. Furthermore, 45 students from Azad High School in Utmanzai were given scholarships to aid in their tuition payment.

In 1946 elections, Congress/Khudai Khidmatgar captured 30 out of 50 legislative seats which provided them an absolute majority. On March 7, 1946, Dr. Khan Sahib formed the ministry. This time the educator Yahya Jan

Khan became the new minister for education. His most notable accomplishment was the acceptance of the Peshawar University bill by the provincial legislature on March 21, 1947.

Approximately Rs 30 lacs were allocated, each year accruing an additional budget of Rs 8 lacs. 88 is a composite of the various constituents like Khan Abdul Qayum Khan Swathi of Hazara, Pir Shahinshah of Kohat, Khan Sahib Sardar Asadullha Khan of Kulachi, Lala Koto Ram of Bannue, Sardar Ram Singh, Abdul Aziz Khan, Sardar Partab Singh, Dr Khan Sahib, and Lala Kewal Ram who took part in the deliberations on the bill which was sponsored by Jan Khan Yahya.

It is striking that none of the members of the Muslim League took part in the discussion on the bill, however, the former accepted the congress ministry's August '47 start and the university's post-partition foundation. Also, in attempt to homogenize the system, 60 vernacular schools were changed to Anglo vernacular schools, and English was taught by different teachers. Moreover, the teachers' salary increases were proportionate.

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